

Automatic movable road divider

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I. Abstract

The Smart Movable Road Divider solution guarantees uninterrupted ambulance access while addressing traffic congestion in urban areas. Conventional road dividers usually have an equal number of lanes, which causes traffic jams during rush hour. In order to address this problem, the idea presents a dynamic system in which IR sensors track traffic density and modify the road divider's position accordingly. The divider shifts to give that side additional lanes when traffic congestion is high, balancing the flow of traffic. Ambulances have a clear road and less traffic latency thanks to this automated approach, which also increases traffic control effectiveness.

II. Introduction

The number of cars on the road has increased proportionately in recent years. The number of vehicles on the road has increased, but the infrastructure remains stagnant and unable to accommodate changes such as congestion and unpredictable journey times. In metropolitan areas, traffic congestion persists as a major concern despite efforts to mitigate it. It has emerged as one of the most significant challenges for urban developers seeking to build sustainable cities with traffic-free lanes. India's traffic is inherently chaotic and noisy. Identifying the magnitude of traffic congestion is critical for characterizing the problem and implementing suitable responses. This study focuses on understanding reoccurring urban congestion, measuring it, taking precautions, and proposing solutions. Widening or building new roads will increase traffic and cause congestion to return to its previous levels. The city's entire available space for the construction of roads, trains, and other modes of transportation is limited. This survey discusses about movable traffic dividers to alleviate congestion in metropolitan areas, as opposed to typical road widening solutions. The road divider that can be moved is designed to maximize the benefits and enhance road capacity.

III. Proposed System

The Proposed System has utilizing flexible and smart techniques, the suggested solution transforms traffic management by prioritizing ambulance clearance and allocating lanes

dynamically. In contrast, the current system uses traditional traffic management techniques with no flexibility, permanent lane allocations and no prioritizing for emergency vehicles. The suggested system's implementation requires the integration of cutting-edge technology including machine learning algorithms and real-time data analytics. These parts prioritize ambulances for quick clearance and dynamically assign lanes based on the flow of traffic. In addition, the system optimizes overall traffic flow and resource use by modifying routing patterns and traffic lights in response to changing conditions. By using this strategy, the suggested solution seeks to improve road networks' efficiency and safety, guaranteeing quick emergency response times and enhancing the commuter experience.

IV. Equipment Configuration

Hardware used:

1. Arduino uno
2. IR sensors
3. Dc motor
4. Buzzer

Software used:

1. Arduino IDE
2. C++

V. Methodology

IoT-enabled automatic movable road divider that function by combining hardware and software elements. The control unit of the system is just an Arduino board, which gets information from sensors mounted to the divider. The amount of traffic on either side of the road is measured by these sensors. A buzzer sound signals indicating the direction of movement needed for the division based on this input. After processing this data, the Arduino board gives instructions to a DC motor, which moves the divider physically and allows the lane allocation to be adjusted as necessary. By using this procedure, lanes are guaranteed to be dynamically assigned according to current traffic conditions. In addition, a monitoring Android app is used simultaneously. This software gives users real-time access to the divider's motions and vehicle counts, giving them valuable information about traffic patterns and lane changes. The hardware of the system senses traffic congestion and signals divider movement, while the software allows for monitoring and control via the Arduino IDE and an Android application. All in all, the system functions flawlessly.

Fig: System Architecture

VI. Results

The automatic road divider system's implementation promises shorter travel times and smoother traffic flow for commuters by dynamically adjusting lane allocations. By accelerating emergency response times and guaranteeing timely clearance for emergency vehicles, it improves road safety. Furthermore, the system maximizes capacity during peak hours by optimizing the usage of the current road infrastructure. By lowering car emissions, its function in easing traffic congestion not only lowers delays but also lessens the impact on the environment. All things considered, the system provides a complete answer for transportation that is safer, more effective, and ecologically friendly.

Fig 1: Smart movable road divider

Fig 2: Working of smart movable road divider

VII. Conclusion

In this study, we have analyzed the traffic congestion problem in a specific area. In order to avoid traffic jams and to shorten the travel time during peak hours, and to provide a rational and better solution for these problems, we have focused on reducing the traffic due to definition of traffic in both directions of the separator. We have also worked on safety measures by informing the drivers of the moment when the divider will be deployed. We will also provide a clear path to the ambulance to ensure that the ambulance reaches the hospital without any delay. We have worked on both time and fuel saving.

VIII. Future scope

In the future, the limitations on increasing road width in developed countries will lead to increased traffic congestion, necessitating alternative traffic control options. The use of modern intelligent transport systems, such as IoT and AI, can facilitate the operation of movable dividers, offering cost-efficient and time-saving benefits. Additionally, there is potential for integrating electrified rails on which the movable dividers would move, serving a dual purpose of facilitating divider movement and charging electric vehicles.

IX. References

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